

EVALUATION OF STRENGTH AND PERMEATION RESISTANCE OF CONCRETE WITH SAWDUST ASH AND GLASS WASTE POWDER AS TERNARY CEMENT COMBINATIONS

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Abstract

The study investigates the potential of utilizing sawdust ash (SDA) and glass waste powder (GWP) as ternary cement replacements in concrete and evaluates their impact on compressive strength and permeation resistance. The experimental program involved the preparation of concrete mixtures with varying proportions of cement, SDA, and GWP at a pre-determined mix ratio, and subsequent testing to assess their mechanical and durability properties. Compressive strength testing was conducted up to 28 days while permeation resistance was evaluated up to 90 days at replacement levels of 30% maximum and compared with control samples thereby measuring the resistance of concrete to the ingress of water and other substances. Seven mix combinations of concrete samples were evaluated at the water/cement (w/c) ratios of 0.35, 0.50, and 0.65 and compressive strengths of 35 to 40 N/mm² were observed at 28-day. At equal w/c ratios, compressive strength decreases with an increase in Void Content (VC) and Water Absorption (WA) resulting from an increase in the content of SDA and GWP. A slight replacement of PC with SDA reduces the strength by 1.05% while a unit substitution of SDA with GWP increases the strength by 1.62%. Also, a unit of SDA increases the VC and WA by 0.94 and 1.03% while a unit of GWP reduces VC and WA by 0.83 and 0.95% respectively. This paper concluded that the inclusion of GWP as a ternary cement component of concrete will improve the compressive strength and permeation resistance of SDA binary cement concrete.

Keywords: sawdust ash, glass waste powder, compressive strength, permeation, absorption.

Introduction

The increasing emphasis on sustainable construction practices has propelled research into alternative materials for concrete production, to enhance both the mechanical and durability properties of

concrete while reducing its environmental impact. One promising avenue of exploration is reducing to the barest minimum, the consumption of PC and this helps in reducing the CO₂ emissions associated with its production. The need for

the use of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as silica fume, fly ash, metakaolin and ground granulated blast furnace slag, sawdust ash and glass waste powder to partially replace PC component of concrete has been found suitable (BS 8500- 1& 2, 2006; Folagbade and Olatunji, 2020). SCMs which are pozzolans and known for their low performance at an early age could be strengthened if proportionally mixed appropriately as binary or ternary blended with PC (Bai et al., 2000; Hassan et al., 2000; Radlinski & Olek, 2012; Folagbade, 2014; Folagbade, 2017; Folagbade and Olatunji, 2020). The potential of these materials to act as ternary cement combinations in concrete has garnered significant interest due to their pozzolanic properties and potential for mitigating the environmental burden associated with traditional cement production.

For example, Folagbade and Newlands, (2014a) posited that, as a result of higher silica content and fineness, the addition of small quantities of metakaolin and silica fume as ternary cement components could improve the performance of fly ash as binary cement at early ages. Various studies as supported, the use of by-products of agricultural wastes products such as rice husk ash (Coutinho, 2003 & Nehdi et al., 2003), cassava peels ash (Ogunbode & Akanmu, 2012), Banana leaf ash, corncob ash (Adesanya & Raheem, 2009, 2010; Akinwumi & Aidomojie, 2015), Bamboo leaf ash and sawdust ash (Udoeyo & Dashibil, 2002; Elinwa & Ejeh, 2004; Raheem et al., 2017) are a good example of SCMs. The studies conclude that due to delayed pozzolanic reactions, all the aforementioned agricultural by-products would reduce strength performance at early ages but improve strength at later ages. To support the use of these agricultural by-products (SDA), ‘the focus of this study is

to investigate on how the strength and durability performance of SDA concrete can be improved for concrete production’. Sawdust being a waste from agricultural products can be easily found in Nigeria and some parts of the world. Despite being domestically available for use as fuel for cooking, the rate of sawdust waste is still high in Nigeria (Oluoti et al., 2014; Olatunji, 2019). Sawdust ash (SDA), a by-product of the wood industry, and glass waste powder, derived from post-consumer glass, have been identified as potential candidates for enhancing the performance of concrete mixtures. A calcined sawdust ash, due to its continuous pozzolanic reaction reduces strength performance at early ages but with increasing curing ages, its strength development and durability performance could be increased at later ages (Obilade, 2014; Folagbade & Aluko, 2019; Folagbade and Olatunji, 2020).

The pozzolanic nature of sawdust ash and the finely ground glass particles can contribute to the development of durable and sustainable concrete structures. However, the effects of incorporating these materials as ternary combinations of cement on the strength and durability of concrete warrant further investigation. Recent studies have explored the individual use of SDA and GWP in concrete, demonstrating their potential to improve certain properties of concrete (Elinwa et al., 2005; Ibrahim, 2006; Raheem et al., 2017). Sawdust ash if mixed in the right proportion, will gain good strength properties, and enhance resistance to permeation with dense microstructure (Folagbade & Aluko, 2019).

Furthermore, Elinwa et al. (2005) postulated that the performance of sawdust ash could be improved by adding small quantities of SCMs with higher silica content. With this improvement, it is also

possible that SDA content of more than 20% could be used in concrete to further reduce the Portland cement content and increase the environmental compatibility of concrete. Glass powder, a good source of silica, will undergo pozzolanic reaction to produce strong, durable, cheap and environmentally compatible concrete when used at 20-30% content to partly replace Portland cement (Shayan & Xu, 2006; Maraghechi et al., 2014; Sadiqul Islam et al., 2017; Folagbade and Olatunji, 2020). However, for the best results, a maximum of 10% replacement level of glass waste powder has been suggested (Sadiqul et al., 2017; Olatunji 2019). Also, due to the alkali-silica reaction in concrete and to prevent concrete from cracking, glass waste powder particles should not be more than 300 μ m size (Folagbade & Olatunji, 2020).

From the foregoing, at equal strength and durability levels, the blending of Sawdust Ash and Glass Waste Powder could permit the addition of higher contents of SCMs and make the blended cement concrete more economical and environmentally friendly than conventional PC concrete. This is because the comparatively lower embodied energy of Sawdust Ash and Glass Waste Powder than that of Portland cement clinker would make the ternary blended cement affordable and more environmentally compatible than Portland Cement". Good concrete will be mechanically strong and durable. 'While the strength of concrete is evaluated with the aid of its compressive strength, its durability will depend on its permeation resistance capacity. Hence, this paper evaluated the compressive strength of concrete, void content (VC) and water absorption (WA) of the ternary cement combinations concrete. Since porosity could be measured by void content, a water absorption test could measure the water absorption capacity of concrete in the

surface zone which could be used in determining its resistance to permeation and the concrete ability to protect the embedded reinforcement against corrosion. Therefore, the results of this research will address the knowledge gap by systematically evaluating the mechanical and durability properties of concrete mixtures containing sawdust ash and glass waste powder as ternary cement replacements.

Experiment Materials and Methods

The cement used for this experiment is Portland Cement (PC), calcined SDA at 600°C and milled GWP. Table 1; shows the chemical compositions of PC, SDA and GWP and the grading curves are presented in Figures 1 &2. Sawdust ash was used as a substitute for PC at 20 and 30% contents in forming the binary cement contents. Glass waste powder was used as a replacement for Sawdust ash cement contents at 5 and 10% in forming the ternary cement components. A limitation of 10% of glass waste powder was observed to achieve the best (Sadiqul Islam et al., 2017; Folagbade & Olatunji, 2020) and 300 μ m maximum of particle sizes were used to reduce the effect of ASR (Ke et al., 2018). Fine aggregates (sand) with a specific gravity of 2.69 and coarse aggregates (granite) with a specific gravity of 2.87 were used, which are within the range of 2.5 to 3.0 for natural aggregates (Neville, 2011; Olatunji, 2019). While the fineness modulus of binders used i.e. PC, SDA and GWP are 0.92, 0.94, 1.03 respectively and specific gravity is 3.13, 2.00, and 2.57 respectively, (Olatunji, 2019). The concrete design was based on the BRE Design Guide (Teychenne et al., 1997) and evaluated at the w/c ratios of 0.35, 0.50 and 0.65 with free water content of 210 kg/m³. Conplast SP390 superplasticiser in conformity with BS EN 934-2 (2009) was used for concrete production and a slump of between 50 and

90 mm in conformity with BS EN 206- 1, 2000 was obtained.

Figure 1: Grading curves for Aggregate

Figure 2: Grading curves of Binders

Table 1: Chemical composition of Portland Cement, Sawdust Ash and Glass Waste Powder

Chemical constituents	Portland cement	Sawdust ash	Glass waste powder
SiO ₂	21.06	69.52	71.14
Al ₂ O ₃	5.17	4.25	2.05
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.82	1.95	0.68
CaO	62.77	8.87	10.82
MgO	2.18	4.32	2.48
Na ₂ O	0.24	0.06	11.42
K ₂ O	0.78	2.45	0.66
SO ₃	2.86	1.07	0.12
TiO ₂	-	-	0.09
CaCO ₃	-	4.80	-
Cr ₂ O ₃	-	-	0.11
P ₂ O ₅	-	-	0.05
LOI	2.12	2.71	0.38
SiO ₂ +Al ₂ O ₃ +Fe ₂ O ₃	-	75.72	73.87

Concrete was mixed following BS EN 12390- 2, (2000), placed in a mould and kept under room temperature for 24hrs before placing into portable water for curing. Hardened concrete specimens were used to carry out Compressive strength, VC and WA tests. Compressive strength was carried out in conformity with BS EN 12390- 3, (2002) using 100 mm cube samples cured for 7, 14, 21 and 28 days. Void content was carried out after the curing ages of 28-, 60- and 90 days following ASTM C642 (2006). This involved determining the mass of the specimen oven-dried to constant mass at 105°C (X), the mass of the specimen after immersion to constant mass in water and boiling (Y), and the apparent mass of the specimen after immersion, boiling and suspension in water (Z).

$$\%, \text{Void content} = \frac{Y-X}{Y-Z} * 100\%$$

Water Absorption Test was carried out after 28, 60 and 90 days of curing in water in conformity with BS 1881- 208, (1996)

using 100 mm concrete cube samples which were oven dried to constant mass at 105°C. This is necessary since the water absorption test is sufficient for evaluating the effect of absorption due to driving rain on the surface of concrete structures (BS 1881-208, 1996). A water absorption test was carried out after the specimens had been water-cured for 28, 60 and 90 days, by the test method described in BS 1881 part 122. For the water absorption test, 108 samples of 100 mm cubes were tested. The specimens were dried in an oven at a temperature of 105°C to constant weight or 72 ± 2 hours. On removal from the oven, the specimens were cooled in a dry airtight vessel and each specimen was weighed (W_1). The specimens were then completely immersed in water at a depth of 25 mm above the samples for 24 hours. After removal, the specimens were shaken, and cleaned with dry cloth to remove free water from its surface and weighed (W_2). Then, the percentage of water absorption was obtained using

$$\% \text{ water absorption} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100\%$$

where W_1 = dry weight and W_2 = wet weight.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The results of the compressive strength, void content and water absorption test of concrete at different replacement levels of SDA as binary cement component and GWP as ternary cement component, w/c ratios and curing ages up to 28 days for compressive strength development and up to 90 days for void content and water absorption test were presented. Compressive strength was compared at equal w/c ratios while void content and water absorption test were compared at equal w/c ratios, equal 28-day strengths, and equal performance levels.

Compressive Strength

The compressive strength of concrete at different contents of sawdust ash (SDA) and glass waste powder (GWP), water/cement ratios and ages up to 28 days are presented in Table 2. In line with previous studies, compressive strength increased with increasing curing age (due to the formation of more strength-enhancing hydration products) and reduced with increasing water/cement ratio (due to the dilution effect caused by reduction in the quantity of cement). Hence, the strength factors of the cement combination concretes increased with increasing curing age. Also, the reduction in the disparities between the strength factors of the cement combination concretes and that of the 100PC concrete, with increasing curing age, further confirms the pozzolanicity of SDA and GWP and the ability of the supplementary cementitious materials to support later-age strength development.

Table 2: Cube compressive strength of Sawdust Ash and Glass Waste Powder Cement Components of Concrete at varying water/cement ratio

Cement	SDA	GWP	W/C				
				7days	14days	21days	28days
100	0	0	0.35	28.0	38.0	44.0	50.0
			0.50	22.0	31.0	36.5	41.0
			0.65	20.0	29.0	34.0	39.0
80	20	0	0.35	20.0	28.0	33.5	39.0
			0.50	16.0	23.0	28.0	32.0
			0.65	14.5	22.0	26.5	31.2
80	15	5	0.35	23.0	31.5	37.0	42.5
			0.50	18.2	26.0	31.0	35.5
			0.65	16.6	24.5	29.5	34.0
80	10	10	0.35	25.0	34.0	40.0	45.0
			0.50	19.5	28.0	33.0	37.5
			0.65	17.9	26.5	31.3	36.0
70	30	0	0.35	14.0	20.0	24.0	28.0
			0.50	11.5	16.8	20.3	23.5
			0.65	10.5	15.8	19.5	23.0
70	25	5	0.35	19.0	26.0	31.0	36.5
			0.50	15.0	22.0	26.5	30.3
			0.65	14.0	21.0	25.5	29.5
70	20	10	0.35	22.6	30.5	36.2	41.9
			0.50	17.9	25.2	30.0	34.7
			0.65	16.1	23.0	28.6	32.9

Table 3: Strength Factors of Concrete Containing Sawdust Ash and Glass Waste Powder

Cement	SDA	GWP	W/C	Strength factor ^{a)} , (%)					Overall Average	% Reduction
				7d	14d	21d	28d	Average		
100	0	0	0.35	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	-
			0.50	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0			
			0.65	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0			
80	20	0	0.35	71.4	73.7	76.2	78.0	74.9	75.7	24.3
			0.50	72.7	74.2	76.7	78.1	75.5		
			0.65	72.5	75.9	78.0	80.0	76.6		
80	15	5	0.35	82.2	83.0	84.1	85.0	83.6	84.5	15.5
			0.50	82.7	83.9	85.0	86.6	84.6		
			0.65	83.0	84.5	86.5	87.2	85.4		
80	10	10	0.35	89.3	89.5	90.9	90.0	89.9	90.5	9.5
			0.50	88.6	90.3	90.4	91.5	90.2		
			0.65	89.5	91.4	92.1	92.3	91.3		
70	30	0	0.35	50.0	52.7	54.6	56.0	53.4	54.7	45.3
			0.50	52.3	54.2	55.6	57.3	54.9		
			0.65	52.5	54.5	57.4	59	55.9		
70	25	5	0.35	67.9	68.4	70.5	73.0	70.0	71.6	28.4
			0.50	68.2	71.0	72.6	74.4	71.6		
			0.65	70.0	72.4	75.0	75.7	73.3		
70	20	10	0.35	80.4	81.3	82.3	83.8	82.0	82.5	17.5
			0.50	81.4	82.3	83.3	84.7	82.9		
			0.65	80.5	81.7	84.1	84.4	82.7		

a % Reduction of average strength factor at 28 days

By Comparing with 100% PC concrete, strength developed at 28day reduces with an increase in the content of SDA by 24.3 & 45.3% at 20 & 30% total replacement of SDA; this results in strength reductions of 1.09 and 1.07% respectively (mean = 1.08%) for a unit replacement of Portland Cement with SDA. Also, by comparison with the SDA binary cement concretes, the inclusion of 5% GWP as a ternary cement component increased the strength at 28days by 8.8% (24.3 minus 15.5) and 16.9% (45.3 minus 28.4) at the replacement levels of 20 & 30% respectively. These resulted, in compressive strength increases of 1.88 and 1.66% (mean = 1.77%) for a unit replacement of SDA with GWP. Similarly, the inclusion of 10% GWP as a ternary cement component resulted in compressive strength increases of 14.8% (24.3 minus 9.5) and 27.8% (45.3 minus 17.5) at the replacement levels of 20 & 30%

respectively. These also result, in compressive strength increases of 1.48 and 1.55% (mean = 1.52%) for a unit replacement of SDA with GWP. By combining results at the replacement levels, a unit replacement of SDA with GWP results in compressive strength increases of 1.52 and 1.75% (mean = 1.64%). Hence, GWP as a ternary cement component can be used to strengthen the compressive strength development of SDA as a binary cement concrete. This is also supported by Folagbade & Olatunji (2020).

Void Content (VC) and Water Absorption (WA) of Concrete at different Water/Cement (w/c) Ratio

Figures 3 to 8 present the VC and WA of concrete at different replacement levels of SDA and GWP, different w/c ratios and different curing ages. The Figures show that the VC and WA of concrete reduced with

curing age and increased with an increase in the w/c ratio.

VC of Concrete at Different Replacement Levels, Different W/C Ratios & Different Curing Ages

Water Absorption Test of Concrete at Different Replacement Levels Different W/C Ratios & Different Curing Ages

The above figures show that, at equal w/c ratios and curing ages, VC and WA

increase with an increase in SDA contents and reduce with an increase in GWP contents. According to Folagbade & Olatunji (2020), the increase in both WA and SDA content would be recorded as a result of the decrease in Portland cement

content, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and the pozzolanic reaction of SDA and the consequent reduction in the development of sufficient hydration products with less permeable microstructure. The decrease in both VC and WA with an increase in GWP content, as a ternary cement component, could be a result of its higher silica (SiO_2) content resulting in more hydration products that filled the voids in concrete. This is because the silica content present in glass powder will react with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to produce more calcium silicate hydrate gel that would reduce void content (Ke, et al., 2018; Jangid & Saoji, 2015) and therefore reduce the water absorption of the ternary cement concrete.

The table below presents the 90-day analysis of the VC and WA test of concretes. The VC factors and WA test factors measure the differences between the 90-day VC and WA of 100% PC concrete and the blended cement concretes at

different w/c ratios. The table shows that at 90-day VC of concrete increased by 19.96 & 34.03% at 20 and 30% of SDA contents resulting in a percentage increase in void content of 0.90 and 1.00 (mean = 0.95%) for a unit replacement of PC with SDA. With the inclusion of 5% GWP as a ternary cement component, void content at 28 days was reduced by 9.5 and 7.18% at the replacement levels of 20 & 30%. These results in VC reduction percentages of 0.57 and 0.97 (mean = 0.77%) for a unit replacement of SDA with GWP. Similarly, the inclusion of 10% GWP as a ternary cement component resulted in VC reductions of 17.35 and 13.47% at the replacement levels of 20 & 30%. These also result in VC reduction percentages of 0.81 and 0.95 (mean = 0.88%) for a unit replacement of SDA with GWP. Hence, by combining the two replacement levels, a unit replacement of SDA with GWP resulted in VC reduction of 0.76 - 0.86% (mean = 0.81%)’.

Table 3: Analysis of 90-Day Void Content and Water Absorption of Concretes

Mix			W/C	90-Day Void Content			90-Day Water Absorption		
OPC	SDA	GWP		Void Content, %	VCF, %	Average VCF, %	Water Absorption, %	WAF, %	Average WAF, %
100	0	0	0.35	6.5	100.00	100.00	13.95	100.00	100.00
			0.50	7.6	100.00		18.59	100.00	
			0.65	8.6	100.00		20.25	100.00	
80	20	0	0.35	8.4	122.62	119.96	21.91	136.33	127.16
			0.50	9.4	119.15		24.57	124.34	
			0.65	10.5	118.10		25.57	120.81	
80	15	5	0.35	7.3	113.34	110.46	19.92	129.97	121.94
			0.50	8.4	109.52		23.08	119.45	
			0.65	9.4	108.51		24.24	116.46	
80	10	10	0.35	6.7	102.99	102.61	17.93	122.20	115.89
			0.50	7.8	102.57		21.58	113.86	
			0.65	8.8	102.27		22.91	111.61	
70	30	0	0.35	10.5	138.10	134.03	37.17	162.47	156.17
			0.50	11.4	133.33		40.82	154.46	
			0.65	12.4	130.65		41.82	151.58	
70	25	5	0.35	9.3	130.11	126.85	33.30	158.11	151.69
			0.50	10.4	126.92		37.12	149.92	
			0.65	11.2	123.22		38.23	147.03	
70	20	10	0.35	8.5	123.53	120.56	29.43	152.60	146.16
			0.50	9.6	120.84		33.41	144.36	
			0.65	10.4	117.31		34.63	141.53	

The 90-day water absorption of concrete increased by 27.16 and 56.17% at 20 & 30% of SDA contents resulting in increases in water absorption of 0.96 and 1.10 (mean = 1.03%) for a unit replacement of PC with SDA. With the inclusion of 5% GWP, WA at 90-day reduces by 5.22 and 4.48% at the replacement levels of 20 & 30%. These results in WA with the percentage of reduction of 0.75 and 1.17 (mean = 0.96%) for a unit replacement of binary with ternary cement components. Similarly, the inclusion of 10% GWP results in WA reductions of 11.27 and 10.01% at the replacement levels of 20 & 30%. These also result in WA with a percentage reduction of 0.84 and 1.04 (mean = 0.94%) for a unit replacement of binary with ternary cement components. Therefore, by combining the two analyses, a unit replacement of binary with ternary cement components results in WA reduction of 0.94 & 0.96% (mean = 0.95%). Hence, GWP as a ternary cement component could be used to reduce the VC & WA thereby increasing the resistance to permeation and durability properties of SDA blended cement concrete.

Void Content (VC) and Water Absorption (WA) of Concrete at 28-Day Equal Strengths
 Specifications are usually relying on the 28-day strengths in structural concrete design for optimal use. Therefore, to evaluate the permeation resistance of the concretes at equal

28-day strengths, the 28-day compressive strengths in Table 2 and the 28-day VC and WA values in Table 3 have been interpolated against the w/c ratios. Hence, Table 4 presents the w/c ratios at 28-day strengths of 35-40 N/mm² achieved by cement concretes with blended components and the corresponding VC and WA results at these strengths. Table 4 shows that equal strengths with 100PC concrete could be attained by the blended cement concretes at lower w/c ratios. This implies that higher cement content would be needed by the blended cement concretes to achieve equal strengths with 100% PC concrete. By comparison, at an equal replacement level, the SDA binary cement concretes could require lower w/c ratios than the ternary cement concretes to achieve equal strengths with the conventional PC concrete. In addition, the w/c ratios required to achieve equal compressive strengths with that of conventional PC concrete decrease with an increase in the content of SDA as a binary cement component and increase with an increase in the content of GWP as a ternary cement component. This implies that more cement content will be required by the SDA binary cement concretes than the corresponding GWP ternary cement concretes at equal compressive strengths. This is supported by Folagbade & Aluko (2019) and Folagbade & Olatunji (2020). The aforementioned also supports the tendency of GWP to support compressive strength development than SDA.

Table 4: Void Content and Water Absorption at 28-day equal Strength of Concrete

Mix			Compressive Strength at 28 days								
OPC	SDA	GWP	35 N/mm ²			37 N/mm ²			40 N/mm ²		
			W/C	VC	WA	W/C	VC	WA	W/C	VC	WA
100	0	0	*	*	*	0.61	13.0	27.62	0.53	11.9	26.51
80	20	0	0.42	12.2	30.42	0.38	11.7	29.42	0.35	11.4	28.55
80	15	5	0.52	12.7	30.66	0.45	11.9	29.45	0.39	11.2	27.96
80	10	10	0.60	13.0	30.01	0.52	12.0	29.17	0.43	10.9	27.32
70	30	0	0.35	13.5	46.47	*	*	*	*	*	*
70	25	5	0.38	12.6	43.33	0.35	12.3	42.28	*	*	*
70	20	10	0.49	13.1	42.08	0.44	12.5	40.93	0.38	11.7	39.13

Table 4 above shows that “VC and WA of concrete reduces with increase in compressive strength. Also, all the binary and ternary cement concretes up to 30% contents of SDA and GWP have lower VC & WA values recorded and therefore will have higher resistance to permeation than the conventional PC concrete at equal compressive strengths. This observation is supported by Folagbade & Olatunji (2020) which shows that blended cement concretes have the propensity to perform better than conventional PC concrete at equal compressive strengths. Likewise, Table 4 above shows that, at equal compressive strengths, VC and WA of concrete reduce with an increase in SDA content as a binary cement component and increase with an increase in GWP content as a ternary cement component. This tells that, at equal compressive strengths, the inclusion of GWP as a ternary cement component would result in better strength development but not as better resistance to permeation than SDA. Therefore, at equal compressive strengths, SDA will have more durability performance than GWP if the design criterion is solely on the durability performance of concrete. However, since lower w/c ratios with higher contents of PC will be required by the binary than the ternary cement concretes, the final choice will depend on both the environmental and economic implications (material costs) of the concretes at equal compressive strengths or at equal performance levels (Folagbade & Olatunji, 2020)”.

Blended Cement Concrete at Equal Performance Level

By determining “water/cement ratios at which the concrete mixes achieved equal performance at the total replacement levels (20 and 30%) within the limit of this study, the ternary cement concretes require higher water/cement ratios than the binary cement concretes to achieve equal performance

level. Assuming equal materials cost and embodied carbon dioxide (CO₂) contents for SDA and GWP, the binary cement concretes will require high contents of cement and attract high cost of production and embodied CO₂ contents than the ternary cement concretes”. Therefore, it is concluded that ‘the inclusion of GWP as a ternary cement component of concrete will improve the compressive strength and permeation resistance of SDA binary cement concrete’.

Recommendations

This research confirmed that both SDA and GWP as binary and ternary cement supplements prove their binding properties and also indicated that up to 30% replacement of cement with SDA and GWP will be structurally effective and economical for building production. Based on the investigation carried out, the following recommendations were made:

1. To reduce the high cost of Portland cement production, it is required to use local construction materials.
2. Need for encouragement and involvement of professionals, researchers, and private partnerships in the built environment for optimal results.
3. Promotion of locally made blended cement through government policy and enlightenment of the citizens.
4. Provision of adequate mortgage housing through mortgage banks and government for low-income earners.
5. Promotion of locally available and investigated cementitious materials through government policy and finance to encourage researchers thereby enhancing better economic reality.

Conclusion

The study evaluated the strength and permeation resistance of concrete with SDA and GWP as ternary cement combinations thus, the following conclusions were made:

- a. The strength reduces with an increase in w/c ratio and increases with an increase in curing age. Consequently, while void content and water absorption increase with the increase in w/c ratio, void content, and water absorption reduce with an increase in compressive strength and curing ages.
- b. At equal w/c ratios, void content and water absorption increase, and strength reduces with an increase in the quantity of SDA contents. While void content and water absorption reduce and compressive strength increases with increased GWP contents.
- c. At replacement levels up to 30%, 'all the binary and ternary blended cement concrete achieved equal strengths with 100% PC concrete at lower w/c ratios. However, SDA binary cement concretes would require lower w/c ratios than the ternary cement concretes to achieve equal strengths at equal replacement levels.
- d. At equal performance level of strengths, 'all the blended cement concretes resulted in low VC and WA and therefore has a higher resistance to permeation than the conventional PC concrete. Also, at equal performance levels, GWP has a better natural way of improving permeation resistance than SDA.

Therefore, for adequate compressive strength and permeation resistance of concrete, 'the inclusion of GWP will

enhance the use of SDA content of cement up to 30% in concrete and result in structural concrete production with higher resistance to permeation than the conventional PC concrete.

References

- Abdullahi, M. (2006). Characteristics of Wood Ash/ OPC Concrete. *Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practices and Technologies* 8: 9-16.
- Abdulkreem, O. M. (2012). Influence of concrete mix proportions and curing regimes on density, absorption and voids in hardened concrete. *Al-Rafidain Engineering*, **20** (4), 103-117
- Adesanya, D. A., & Raheem, A. A. (2009). A study of the workability and compressive strength characteristics of corncob ash blended cement concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, **23**, 311-317.
- Adesanya, D. A., & Raheem, A. A. (2010). A study of the permeability and acid attack of corncob ash blended cement. *Construction and Building Materials*, **24**, 403-409.
- Akinwumi, I. I., & Aidomojie, O. I. (2015). Effect of corncob ash on the geotechnical properties of lateritic soil stabilized with Portland cement. *International Journal of Geomatics and Geosciences*, **5**(3), 375-392.
- Aluko, O. (2018). *Absorption Characteristics of Sawdust Ash Cement Laterised Concrete*. An Unpublished Master of Science Thesis Submitted to the Department of Building, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria.
- ASTM C642 (2006). Standard test method for density, absorption, and voids in hardened concrete. Pennsylvania:

- American Society for Testing and Materials International.*
- Bai, J., Sabir, B. B., Wild, S., & Kinuthia, J. M. (2000). Strength development in concrete incorporating PFA and metakaolin. *Magazine of Concrete Research*, 52(3), 153-162.
- Bajad, M. N., Modhera, C. D., & Desai, A. K. (2012). *Resistance of concrete containing waste glass powder against MgSO₄ attack.* available at nbncw.com.
- BS EN 197- 1 (2000). Cement- Part 1: Composition, specifications and conformity criteria for common cements. London: *British Standards Institution.*
- BS EN 206- 1 (2000). Concrete- Part 1: Specification, performance, production and conformity. London: *British Standards Institution.*
- BS EN 934-2 (2009). Admixtures for concrete, mortar and grout- Part 2: Concrete admixtures- Definitions, requirements, conformity, marking and labelling. London: *British Standards Institution.*
- BS 8500- 1 (2006). Concrete- Complementary British Standard to BS EN 206- 1- Part 1: Method of specifying and guidance for the specifier. London: *British Standards Institution.*
- BS 8500- 2 (2006). Concrete- Complementary British Standard to BS EN 206- 1- Part 2: Specification for constituent materials and concrete. London: *British Standards Institution.*
- BS EN 12390- 2 (2000). Testing hardened concrete- Part 2: Making and curing specimens for strength tests. London: *British Standards Institution.*
- BS EN 12390- 3 (2002). Testing hardened concrete- Part 3: Compressive strength of test specimens. London: *British Standards Institution.*
- Buari, T.A., Ademola, S.A., & Ayegbokiki, S.T. (2013). Characteristics strength of groundnut shell ash (GSA) and ordinary Portland cement (OPC) blended concrete in Nigeria. *International Organization of Scientific Research Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, 3 (7), 01-07.
- Coutinho, J. S. (2003). The combined benefits of CPF and RHA in improving the durability of concrete structures. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 25, 51-59.
- Dias, W. P. S., Nanayakkara, S. M. A., & Ekneligoda, T. C. (2003). Performance of concrete mixes with OPCPFA Blends. *Magazine of Concrete Research*, 55 (2), 161-170.
- Du, H., & Tan, K. H. (2015). Transport properties of concrete with glass powder as a supplementary cementitious material. *American Concrete Institute (ACI) Materials Journal*, 112 (3), 429-437.
- Elinwa, A. U., & Ejeh, S. P. (2004). Effects of incorporation of sawdust waste incineration fly ash in cement pastes and mortars. *Journal of Asian Architecture and Building Engineering*, 3(1), 1-7.
- Elinwa, A. U., Ejeh, S. P., & Akpabio, I. O. (2005). Using metakaolin to improve sawdust ash concrete. *Concrete International*, 27(11), 49-52.
- Folagbade, S. O. (2014). Influence of fly ash and silica fume on the compressive strength development of Portland cement concrete. *Journal of Environmental Design and Management*, 6(1 & 2), 36-50.
- Folagbade, S. O., & Newlands M. (2014a).

- Compressive strength development of blended cement concretes containing Portland cement, fly ash and metakaolin. *The Indian Concrete Journal*, 88(9), 20-29.
- Folagbade, S. O., & Newlands, M. D. (2014b). Suitability of cement combinations for carbonation resistance of structural concrete. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 12(4), 423-439.
- Folagbade, S. O. (2016). Absorption characteristics of cement combination concrete containing Portland cement, fly ash and metakaolin. *Civil Engineering Dimension*, 18(1), 57-64.
- Folagbade, S. O. (2017). Early-age performance of cement combination concrete. *Civil Engineering Dimension*, 19(1), 14-20.
- Folagbade, S. O. (2017). Water Absorption Characteristics of Concrete Containing Fly Ash and Silica Fume, *Journal of Environmental Design and Management*, Faculty of Environmental Design and Management, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria, 9(1), 47-56.
- Folagbade, S. O. (2018). Effect of sawdust ash on the compressive strength and sorptivity of laterised concrete. *Civil and Environmental Research*, 10(10), 5-14.
- Folagbade, S. O., & Aluko, O. (2019). Permeation resistance of sawdust ash blended cement laterized concrete. *Civil Engineering Dimension*, 21(2), 76-83.
- Folagbade, S.O., & Olatunji, A.S. (2020): Effect of Glass Waste Powder on the Compressive Strength and Permeation Properties of Concrete Containing Portland Cement and Sawdust Ash. *Civil and Environmental Research*, vol 12, No 4 pp 36-48.
- Hardik Dhull, (2017). Effect of Properties of Concrete by Using Sawdust Ash as Partial Replacement of Cement. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*. ISSN 2319-8753, 6(9).
- Hassan, K. E., Cabrera, J. G., & Maliehe, R. S. (2000). The effect of mineral admixtures on the properties of high-performance concrete. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 22 (4), 267-271.
- Jangid J.B. & Saoji A.C. (2015). Comparative study of waste glass powder as the partial replacement of cement in concrete production-A laboratory investigation. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 3 (2), 063– 066.
- Ke, G., Li, W., Li, R., Li, Y., & Wang, G. (2018). Mitigation effect of waste glass powders on alkali-silica reaction (ASR) expansion in cementitious composite. *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, 12(67).
- Khatib, J. M., Negim, E. M., Sohl, H. S., & Chileshe, N. (2012). Glass powder utilisation in concrete production. *European Journal of Applied Sciences*, 4(4), 173-176.
- Kolawole J. T., Olusola K. O., & Ata O. (2015). Strength of bamboo leaf ash and pulverized burnt clay waste blended cement concrete. *International Organization of Scientific Research Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE)*, 12 (6), 36-42.
- Obilade, I. O. (2014). Use of sawdust ash as a partial replacement for cement in concrete. *International Journal of*

- Engineering Science Invention*, 3(8), 36-40.
- Oluoti, K., Megwai, G., Petterson, A., & Richards, T. (2014). Nigerian wood waste: A dependable and renewable fuel option for power production. *World Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 2, 234-248.
- Olutoge, F. A. (2016). Effect of waste glass powder (WGP) on the mechanical properties of concrete. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 5 (11), 213-220.
- Radlinski, M., & Olek, J. (2012). Investigation into the synergistic effects in ternary cementitious systems containing Portland cement, fly ash and silica fume. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 34(4), 451-459.
- Raheem, A. A., Adedokun, S. I., Ajayi, B. R., Adedoyin, O. A., & Adegboyega, B. O. (2017). Application of sawdust ash as a partial replacement for cement in the production of interlocking paving stones. *International Journal of Sustainable Construction Engineering and Technology*, 8(1), 1-11.
- Sadiqul Islam, G. M., Rahman, M. H., & Kazi, N. (2017). Waste glass powder as partial replacement of cement for sustainable concrete practice. *International Journal of Sustainable Built Environment*, 6, 37-44.
- Shayan, A., & Xu, A. (2006). Performance of glass powder as a pozzolanic material in concrete: A field trial on concrete slabs. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 36(3), 457-468.
- Teychenne, D. C., Franklin, R. E., & Erntroy, H. C. (1997). Design of normal concrete mixes (2nd ed.) amended by B. K. Marsh. Watford: *Building Research Establishment*.
- Udoeyo, F. F., & Dashibil, P. U. (2002). Sawdust ash as a concrete material. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 14(2), 173-176.
- Zidol A., Tognonvi M. T. & Tagnit-Hamou A. (2017). Effect of glass powder on concrete sustainability. *New Journal of Glass and Ceramics*, 7, 34-47.